

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
An open science journal for environmental health research

Evaluation Report (triage round 3) for **TEBT-2023-0005**

Submission Information Table

Submission Title	Evidence-based approaches in toxicology: their origins, challenges and future directions
Submission Reference	TEBT-2023-0005
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley
Number of Reviewers	2 (dual editorial review)
Submission Type	Expert Commentary ▾
Preprint DOI	https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8190841
Evaluation Date	20 Jul 2024
Evaluation Round	Editorial review round 3
Recommendation	Accept ▾
Handling Editor's Explanation for Recommendation	The authors have made significant revisions based on the previous round of comments, with the new version now being acceptable for publication.

Summary of article

This Expert Commentary recounts the introduction and future path of the use of evidence-based methods in toxicology. It uses as a focal point the inception, development and vision of the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (EBTC). The article should serve as a useful primer for those interested in some of the key features of evidence-based toxicology, where and when the concept originated, and how it is now understood and being developed.

Acceptance note

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor after two rounds of revision in response to two rounds of editorial review. During editorial review, the editors recommended developing the focus and argumentation of the article, to improve how the history and key concepts of evidence-based toxicology were communicated to the reader. The authors addressed these issues through extensive and thoughtful revisions, leading to a significantly improved submission.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8338400>.